

1 Polysaccharide-Potato Protein Coacervates for Enhanced Anthocyanin 2 Bioavailability and Stability

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10 Abstract

11 Anthocyanins (ACNs) possess strong antioxidants, anti-cancer, anti-obesity, anti-diabetic, and
12 anti-inflammatory properties but are limited use by their susceptibility to environmental factors.
13 This study aims to overcome these limitations by developing and assessing a novel coacervate
14 system, consisting of potato protein isolate (PPI) combined with various polysaccharides, to
15 stabilize and encapsulate anthocyanins from black carrot concentrate. The polysaccharides
16 included in this system include inulin, gum Arabic, guar gum, pectin, and soluble fiber. The
17 coacervate system's effectiveness in maintaining stability and increasing the bioavailability of
18 anthocyanins was evaluated compared to conventional soybean protein-based systems. The
19 results show that pH considerably influences potato protein solubility, with maximum solubility
20 at strongly acidic (pH 2) conditions. Hygroscopicity and moisture content analysis of the
21 coacervates showed significant variations, with potato protein-guar gum (PPIGG) microcapsules
22 having the lowest moisture content and potato protein gum Arabic (PPIGA) microcapsules having
23 the highest moisture content. SEM imaging illustrated distinct microcapsule morphologies, while
24 FT-IR measurement verified the successful integration of proteins and polysaccharides. The
25 significance of the research reflects its proof that potato protein isolate (PPI) based coacervate
26 systems consists of potato protein with polysaccharides, particularly those containing gum Arabic
27 and pectin, have significant potential for improving anthocyanin stability and bioavailability.
28 These findings guide future studies to investigate other polysaccharides, improve coacervation
29 processes, and explore applications in the food and nutraceutical sectors. It also offers valuable
30 insights for creating efficient encapsulation techniques for bioactive substances.

31 **Keywords:** Black carrot anthocyanin, double emulsion, microencapsulation, protein-
32 polysaccharide interactions

33

341. **Introduction**

35 Natural antioxidants are becoming more vital in the challenge against chronic illnesses
36 and to improve human health. Among these, anthocyanins (ANCs) are sustainable natural
37 colorants found primarily in fruits, vegetables, and cereals. ANCs, the predominant group of
38 water-soluble flavonoids, impart vivid red, purple, and blue hues to plants. ANCs are well-known
39 for their anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, anti-obesity, anti-diabetic, and antioxidant properties [1].
40 Despite their promising therapeutic potential, the applicability of anthocyanins is significantly
41 limited by their sensitivity to environmental factors such as pH, temperature, and light,
42 necessitating the development of novel preservation and delivery techniques [2].

43 Microencapsulation, which captures free pigments into wall materials, may preserve and
44 control anthocyanin release [3]. Complex coacervation, a physicochemical microencapsulation
45 technique involving phase separation, is driven by the interaction of two or more oppositely
46 charged colloids - typically proteins and polysaccharides - resulting in a significant reduction of
47 the system's free electrostatic energy through the interaction between oppositely charged ions
48 [4,5]. Protein-polysaccharide nano-assemblies are practical tools with which to build carrier
49 systems with outstanding biosafety and biocompatibility, as well as great potential and economic
50 viability. Because of the wide variety of protein and polysaccharide polymers found in biological
51 systems, customized protein-polysaccharide nanocomposites containing bioactive compounds
52 may be created by combining various polymer combinations. As a result, versatile delivery
53 systems may be constructed using protein-polysaccharide nanoconjugates [6]. The protein-
54 polysaccharide complex demonstrated superior emulsifying qualities when applied in
55 combination because of its increased chemical and colloidal stability compared to the separate
56 biopolymers [7].

57 Given the rising emphasis on environmental sustainability and public health, there is a
58 growing demand for sustainable, health-conscious encapsulation systems. Traditional
59 encapsulation techniques, which frequently use animal proteins, have recently been criticized
60 because of their possible allergic reactions, adverse environmental effects, and ethical dilemmas
61 [8]. The context above emphasizes the need to investigate plant-based encapsulation systems,
62 which hold the promise of providing renewable, non-toxic, and biodegradable alternatives that

63 adhere to sustainability and green chemistry principles [9]. Potato proteins are a great option since
64 they are highly soluble in water [10].

65 Black carrot anthocyanins, which provide bright colors and significant health benefits due
66 to their antioxidant properties, are widely used in the food industry as natural colorants for
67 products such as beverages, confectioneries, and jellies [10]. They are exceptionally high in
68 anthocyanins, which give bright hues and provide considerable health advantages due to their
69 antioxidant characteristics [11]. However, it is challenging to create an efficient encapsulating
70 technology that protects these sensitive compounds from environmental factors while preserving
71 their bioavailability and functional characteristics.

72 According to recent studies, numerous plant-based systems can potentially encapsulate
73 bioactive chemicals. Gum Arabic, for example, has been used because of its film-forming and
74 stabilizing qualities [12]. However, there are remaining uncertainties about how effectively
75 specific polysaccharides function in combination with potato protein isolate to stabilize
76 anthocyanins. To address this issue, this study investigates the use of potato protein isolate in
77 combination with various polysaccharides—including inulin, gum Arabic, guar gum, pectin, and
78 soluble fiber—to develop a coacervate system for the encapsulation and stabilization of black
79 carrot anthocyanins.

80 This study aims to evaluate the efficiency of innovative plant-based coacervate systems
81 and conventional soybean protein-based systems in maintaining the stability and improving the
82 bioavailability of anthocyanins. By solving these issues, the study seeks to advance sustainable
83 encapsulation technologies and address the increasing need for food products that are both health-
84 and environmentally conscious. To provide a thorough assessment of their prospective uses in the
85 food industry, this study investigates the solubility, moisture content, hygroscopicity, antioxidant
86 activity, and encapsulation efficiency of developed coacervates.

87

88 **2. Materials and Methods**

89 **2.1. Materials**

90 Black carrot juice concentrate (ACN content: 5.577 g/L), the anthocyanin source, was obtained
91 from Bart (Warsaw, Poland). The encapsulating matrix comprised potato protein which has 83.6%
92 crude protein content, obtained from Przedsiębiorstwo Przemysłu Ziemniaczanego S.A.
93 (Niechlów, Poland), along with several polysaccharides and other components: gum Arabic from
94 Natur sklep (Wrocław, Poland), guar gum from Green Essence - Sklep Zielarsko (Szczecin,
95 Poland), inulin and maltodextrin from Agnex (Białystok, Poland), pectin from "Smakosz" Maciej

96 Piotrowski (Brzeziny, Poland), and NUTRIOSE[®] FM06, a soluble fiber, from Roquette Frères
97 (Lestrem, France).

98

99 **2.2. Preparation of microcapsules**

100 To prepare the coacervate system, 100 mL of 1% potato protein isolate (PPI) mixed with 100 mL
101 of a 1% polysaccharide gum solutions (gum Arabic, guar gum, inulin, pectin, and soluble fiber)
102 in a 1% concentration each. This mixture was adjusted to a pH of 9. Following pH adjustment,
103 1% Tween 80 solution was added to facilitate emulsification. After that, water-in-oil emulsion
104 (W1/O) containing a 1:1 (g/g) ratio of black carrot (BC) juice concentrate and grapeseed oil
105 (Basso, S.Michele di Serino (AV) Italy) was introduced to the system as 1% and homogenized
106 thoroughly. The emulsion was then carefully mixed while the pH was lowered to 3.5 to induce
107 coacervation. In the last step of this mixture, maltodextrin was added at 1% concentration to aid
108 in the drying process. The final step involved mixing the coacervate system continuously for 30
109 minutes, after which it was subjected to spray drying. To attain the ideal level of dryness without
110 causing any degradation to the encapsulated components, the drying parameters were adjusted at
111 an intake temperature of 150 °C and an output temperature of 75 °C. A control was also prepared
112 using a 1:1 mixture of soy protein isolate (SB) and gum Arabic (GA). Each experiment was
113 conducted in triplicate.

114 **2.3. Potato protein solubility in water**

115 This was assessed using the procedure provided by Ogunwolu et al.[13], in which 200 mg of each
116 protein sample was dissolved in 20 ml deionized water, and the pH of the mixture was changed
117 using 1 N HCl and 1 N NaOH to 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, and 12. The mixture was agitated for 30 minutes
118 at room temperature (about 22 °C). After that, it was centrifuged for 15 minutes at 9,000 rpm.
119 Bradford kit technique (1976) was used to determine the protein concentration in the supernatant.
120 Following that, the solubility of the protein was calculated:

121

$$122 \quad \text{Solubility (PS) (\%)} = \frac{\text{Protein content of supernatant}}{\text{Total protein content of the sample}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

123

124 **2.4. Electrophoresis on sodium dodecyl sulphate–polyacrylamide gel (SDS-PAGE)**

125 Sodium dodecyl sulfate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) was used under
126 reducing conditions to analyze the molecular weight distribution of PPI and coacervates [14].
127 The 4-20% Mini-PROTEAN[®] TGX[™] Precast Protein Gel (Bio-Rad, USA) and Precision Plus

128 Protein™ Dual Color Standards (10-250 kDa) were employed as molecular weight markers. The
129 samples were prepared by dissolving samples in Laemmli buffer (0.5 M Tris-HCl, pH 6.8),
130 containing 75 mM 1,4-dithiothreitol, 3% SDS, 10% glycerol, and 0.01% bromophenol blue. The
131 sample concentration was adjusted to 2-3 mg/mL as verified by the Bradford assay.
132 The samples were then homogenized (10,000 rpm for 2 minutes) using a T18 digital homogenizer
133 with an S18N-10G dispersing tool. Following homogenization, the samples were denatured by
134 heating at 95°C for 5 minutes and centrifuged at 13,000 rpm for 15 minutes at 4°C to remove
135 particulates. Aliquots of 10 µL of the supernatant were then loaded onto the gel.
136 Electrophoresis was performed at a constant voltage of 95-120 V using a running buffer
137 consisting of 0.25 M Tris, 1.92 M glycine, and 0.5% SDS. After electrophoresis, the gels were
138 washed with MilliQ water and stained for 1 hour with Coomassie Brilliant Blue G250 (0.005%)
139 in a solution of 50% methanol, 40% water, and 10% glacial acetic acid. Gels were destained in
140 10% methanol and 7.5% glacial acetic acid for 24 hours, followed by visualization using Image
141 Lab™ Software with the Molecular Imager Gel Doc™ XR1 system (Bio-Rad, CA, USA).

142

143 **2.5. Moisture content**

144 The moisture content of the samples was determined by drying 0.2 g of each sample in an oven
145 at 105 °C for a minimum of two hours. The drying process was repeated until a constant weight
146 was achieved. The moisture content was calculated as the percentage weight loss, representing
147 the difference between the initial sample weight and the weight after drying [15].

148 **2.6. Hygroscopicity**

149 The hygroscopicity of the samples was assessed following the protocol established by Shaddel et
150 al. [16]. Precisely, 0.2 g of each freeze-dried sample was placed in a Petri dish and stored in a
151 desiccator containing a saturated solution of Na₂SO₄ for one week. Hygroscopicity was expressed
152 as the grams of water absorbed per 100 g of the sample, with all measurements conducted in
153 triplicate.

154 **2.7. Particle Size**

155 Particle size distribution was measured using a Morphologi® G3SE device with a dry sample
156 dispersion unit provided by Malvern Instruments Ltd., UK. The relative volume of particles
157 within specific size ranges was used to generate the particle size distribution curves, analyzed
158 using Malvern Microsoft software v.5.40. Key parameters, including the largest particle size (D_v,

159 0.9]), median particle volume ($D[v, 0.5]$), and smallest particle size ($D[v, 0.1]$), were evaluated.
160 The Span index (SI) was calculated using the formula:

$$161 \quad SI = \frac{D_{90} - D_{10}}{D_{50}} \quad (2)$$

162 **2.8. Solubility of microcapsules**

163 The solubility of the samples was determined using a modified method described by Shittu and
164 Lawal [17]. One gram of powdered sample was added to 10 mL of distilled water and stirred for
165 30 minutes. The resulting suspension was centrifuged at 6,000 rpm for 5 minutes, and the
166 supernatant was collected and dried at 105 °C for 24 hours. The solubility percentage was
167 calculated as the ratio of dried solid mass to the powder's initial mass.

168 **2.9. Determination of antioxidant activity**

169 Antioxidant extracts from the microcapsules were prepared based on the method by Kanha et al.
170 [3], with slight modifications. Microcapsules (10 mg) were dispersed in 10 mL of distilled water
171 and stirred for 30 minutes to ensure complete redispersion and emulsion breakdown. The
172 mixtures were subsequently filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper, yielding microcapsule
173 extracts at a concentration of 1 mg/mL, which were then analyzed for antioxidant activity by the
174 DPPH• method [15]. The antioxidant activity of the samples was determined by preparing a
175 solution of 0.06 mmol/L methanol DPPH• (Sigma-Aldrich Inc., USA). The solution's absorbance
176 was measured and corrected to 0.7 ± 0.02 using methanol before storage in the dark. The adjusted
177 absorbance was recorded as 0 min. Then, 50 μ L of the sample or solvent (for control) was
178 combined with 1.95 mL of the DPPH• solution. The mixture was incubated in the dark for 30
179 minutes, and the absorbance was measured at 517 nm. The results were expressed as μ mol
180 trolox/g.

181 **2.10. Anthocyanin Stability**

182 The influence of pH (1, 4, and 7) and temperature (25°C and 90°C) on anthocyanin stability was
183 evaluated [18]. To examine the effect of pH, a 0.1 M citric acid solution was adjusted to pH 1
184 using 0.1 M HCl, and diluted BC was added to this solution until an absorbance of 0.9 at the
185 $\lambda_{\text{vis-max}}$ (520 nm) was achieved. The final volume of the solution was then adjusted to 5 mL
186 using citric acid at pH 1. The same dilution method was applied for pH 4 and pH 7, using a citrate-
187 phosphate buffer (0.2 M Na_2HPO_4 and 0.1 M citric acid) prepared at the respective pH values.
188 The sealed samples were stored in the dark at 25°C. Measurements were taken at 0, 60, 180, 360

189 and 420 minutes, and the absorbance spectrum was recorded within the range of 400-700 nm.
190 The degradation index (DI) was determined as the ratio of $Abs_{420}/Abs_{\lambda\text{-vis-max}}$.
191 To assess the effect of temperature, the pH 1 solution was prepared as described above and
192 incubated at either 25°C or 90°C in a water bath. The DI was measured at regular intervals over
193 time (0, 30, 60, 90, 120, 150, and 180) in the same manner as described for pH stability.

194 **2.11. Encapsulation Efficiency**

195 Microencapsulation efficiency (MEE) was evaluated following the methodology by Kanha et al.
196 [3], with modifications. Total anthocyanin content in the microcapsules (TACm) and on the
197 surface (SACm) were measured spectrophotometrically using the pH differential method after
198 breaking down the microcapsules. For TACm determination, 1 mL of distilled water was added
199 to 100 mg of microcapsules, followed by vigorous shaking using a vortex mixer for 2 minutes
200 and the addition of 4 mL of 99% ethanol. The mixture was vortexed for 5 minutes, centrifuged at
201 6,000 rpm for 5 minutes, and the supernatant was analyzed. SACm was determined by adding 5
202 mL of ethanol, vortexing for 30 seconds, centrifuging at 6,000 rpm for 5 minutes, and analyzing
203 the supernatant. MEE was calculated as follows:

$$204 \quad MEE(\%) = \frac{TACm - SACm}{TACm} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

205 **2.12. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)**

206 Thermal properties of the materials were analyzed using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC
207 1) from Mettler Toledo, conducted under a nitrogen atmosphere with a flow rate of 100 cm³/min,
208 based on the method by Zhao et al. [19] [19] with slight modifications. Each sample (5.0 ± 0.1
209 mg) was placed in a 40 μL aluminum pan and sealed. The DSC scans were performed at a rate of
210 10 °C/min, ranging from 10 °C to 230 °C. The onset, peak, and end temperatures and the areas
211 under the peaks (ΔH) were determined using the STARE software.

212 **2.13. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR)**

213 FT-IR analysis was conducted using a NicoletTMiSTM 10 spectrometer (Thermo Fisher
214 Scientific, Waltham, MA), operating within the wavelength range of 4000-400 cm⁻¹. The spectra
215 were analyzed using the OMNIC software provided by Thermo Fisher Scientific. The models
216 were based on the use of a second derivative of baseline corrected, normalized, multiplicative
217 scatter corrected, and smoothed absorbance value (a.u) from the range of 800–1180 cm⁻¹
218 [20,21].

219 **2.14. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)**

220 The morphology of the microcapsules was observed using a Phenom XL scanning electron
221 microscope, operating at an accelerated voltage of 5 kV, by the method by Przybył et al. [22]. A
222 small amount of the powdered sample was placed on double-sided adhesive tape affixed to the
223 sample support and then flushed with compressed air to remove unattached particles. The sample
224 was subsequently coated with gold using a Cressington 108auto coater and examined under the
225 SEM.

226 **2.15. Color Measurement**

227 The color of the microcapsules was measured using a Minolta CR-400 colorimeter (Konica
228 Minolta Inc., Japan) utilizing the CIELab measurement system. Parameters L, a*, and b* were
229 determined using a specific attachment designed for powdered samples. A 5 mm thick layer of
230 microcapsules was placed in the attachment, and color measurements were performed in
231 triplicate.

232 **2.16. Anthocyanin Retention: chromatographic determination method**

233 Anthocyanins were extracted from black carrot juice concentrate and microcapsules using a
234 salting-out assisted liquid-liquid extraction (SALLE) method with slight modifications [20].
235 Briefly, 1 of microcapsules was mixed with 5 mL each of water and acetonitrile (ACN) in a 15
236 mL falcon tube and vortexed for 20 minutes. After adding 1 g of ammonium sulfate and vortexing
237 for another 5 minutes, the mixture was centrifuged at 6,500 rpm for 10 minutes. The upper layer
238 (1 mL) was evaporated under nitrogen, reconstituted in 1 mL of 10% formic acid solution, filtered
239 through a 0.22 µm membrane, and analyzed via High Performance Liquid Chromatography-
240 Ultraviolet Detection (HPLC-UV) and HPLC-tandem Mass Spectrometry (HPLC-MS/MS).

241 For HPLC -UV determination of the anthocyanins, an Accela high-performance liquid
242 chromatography (HPLC) system linked to an Accela Photo Diode Array (PDA) detection system
243 from Thermo Fisher Scientific (USA) was employed [23]. Anthocyanins separation was carried
244 out using a 5µm Zorbax SB-C18 column (4.6 x 150 mm) manufactured by Agilent Technologies.
245 The mobile phase consisted of a blend of 10% formic acid aqueous solution (A) and acetonitrile
246 (B) at a flow rate of 1 mL/min. The mobile phase gradient started at 98% A and maintained this
247 level for 5 minutes. Subsequently, it underwent a gradual reduction, reaching 75% A by minute
248 20. It swiftly dropped to 0% A by minute 21, then promptly returned to 100% A by minute 23,
249 and ultimately reverted to the initial conditions by minute 25. The PDA detector was programmed
250 to scan within the range of 200-600 nm, while specifically monitoring the maximum UV
251 absorbance of the anthocyanins between 510-540 nm.

252 HPLC-MS/MS analysis used the same HPLC setup coupled with a Thermo Scientific LCQ
253 Fleet™ Ion Trap system and a Kinetex C18 column (2.5 μm, 50 x 2.10 mm) from Phenomenex
254 (USA), employing a mobile phase flow of 200 μL/min. The mobile phase was 1% formic acid
255 (A) and acetonitrile (B). The gradient program started at 95% A, and decreased down to 67% A
256 over 12.5 minutes, with a return to initial conditions by minute 15. The electrospray ionization
257 (ESI) probe operated at 350 °C and 3.5 kV, with nitrogen gas for sheath, auxiliary, and sweep
258 functions. CID used 35% collision energy, and the mass spectrum was monitored from 50 to 1000
259 m/z in SCAN mode. This method enabled precise identification and quantification of
260 anthocyanins in the samples.

261

262 2.17. Statistical analysis

263 Significant differences between mean values assessed by one-way analysis of variance were
264 denoted by a $p \leq 0.05$. (ANOVA). At $p \leq 0.05$, the Tukey post hoc test was employed to identify
265 statistically significant results. Statistica 13.3 software (StatSoft, Inc., Tulsa, USA) was used for
266 this study.

267

2683. Results and Discussion

269 3.1. Effects of pH on water solubility of potato protein

270

271 **Fig. 1.** Solubility of potato protein in different pH levels

272 The solubility of potato protein in water was assessed at pH values ranging from 2 to 12.
273 As shown in Figure 1, the results suggest that variations in pH have a considerable impact
274 on the solubility of potato protein. The solubility was found to be highest at pH 2 (76.79%)

275 and lowest at pH 12 (6.79%). At a highly acidic pH (pH 2), potato protein had the
276 maximum solubility (76.79%). The protonation of amino acid side chains, which
277 increases electrostatic repulsion and causes protein molecules to unfold, is responsible for
278 improved solubility at low pH and enhances the interaction of the molecules with water
279 [24].

280 Potato protein solubility dropped to 62.36% and 52.19%, respectively, when pH rose to 4
281 and 6. . The decrease in solubility around the isoelectric point (pH 4-6) can be explained
282 by the minimal net charge on the protein molecules, which results in decreased
283 electrostatic repulsion and increased protein-protein interactions, causing aggregation and
284 precipitation [25]. Surprisingly, at pH 8, the potato protein solubility rose again to 63.76%.
285 Protein molecules become more soluble in the basic pH range when side chains of amino
286 acids deprotonate. This process raises the net negative charge on the protein molecules,
287 which promotes solubility through greater electrostatic repulsion and hydration [26].
288

289 3.2. Electrophoresis

290 The SDS-PAGE results in Figure SA1 display the molecular weight distribution of the
291 proteins from PPI and coacervates. Key proteins, including lipoxygenase (~94 kDa),
292 patatin (~40-45 kDa), and potato protease inhibitors (~20-25 kDa), are observed in the gel
293 image [27]. The absence of bands in the coacervate samples indicates partial protein
294 degradation and complexation with polysaccharides, suggesting that the coacervates are
295 less intact in the encapsulation process.
296

297 3.3. Evaluation of moisture

298 Moisture content varied significantly among the samples, ranging from 0.04% to 1.72%.
299 Potato protein isolate-gum Arabic (PPIGA) microcapsules exhibited the highest moisture
300 content ($1.72 \pm 0.63\%$), while potato protein isolate-guar gum (PPIGG) microcapsules
301 had the lowest moisture content ($0.04 \pm 0.02\%$) in Table 1. PPIGA microcapsules had the
302 most significant moisture content, possibly due to gum Arabic's hygroscopic nature [28].
303 Gum Arabic is a highly water-soluble polymer capable of absorbing and retaining
304 moisture. The combination of potato protein isolate and gum Arabic may have created a
305 more porous and less cohesive wall structure, allowing for more moisture absorption
306 [29,30].

307 In contrast, the lowest moisture content in the PPIGG microcapsules can be attributed to
308 guar gum's low water-binding capacity when combined with potato protein isolate [31].
309 The reduced moisture content suggests that PPIGG microcapsules may have better
310 stability and longer shelf life under conditions where low moisture is desired. Overall, the
311 moisture content results highlight the impact of different polysaccharides on the water
312 retention properties of potato protein-based microcapsules.

313 3.4. **Moisture absorption capacity**

314 The hygroscopicity of the microcapsules was determined, and the results are presented in
315 Table 1. Hygroscopicity values, expressed as grams of water absorbed per 100 g of
316 sample, varied among the different formulations. The hygroscopicity values for soybean
317 protein-gum Arabic (SBGA) (179.29 ± 3.00 g/100 g) and PPIGA (179.22 ± 3.09 g/100 g)
318 microcapsules were comparable, reflecting the similar moisture absorption characteristics
319 of these formulations. The role of gum Arabic's emulsifying and stabilizing properties
320 contributes to the moderate hygroscopicity observed in these microcapsules [32].

321 The highest hygroscopicity was observed in the potato protein isolate-pectin (PPIP)
322 microcapsules. This high value suggests that combining potato protein isolate with pectin
323 produces microcapsules with a strong affinity for water absorption. The hydrophilic nature
324 of pectin, which forms gels and binds water effectively, likely contributes to the increased
325 hygroscopicity [33]. In contrast, the potato protein isolate-inulin (PPII) microcapsules
326 showed the lowest hygroscopicity. Inulin, a polysaccharide with a lower water-binding
327 capacity than pectin, likely contributes to the reduced hygroscopicity of the PPII
328 microcapsules. As a fructooligosaccharide (FOS), inulin comprises fructose units linked
329 with β -(2-1) links that exhibit varying degrees of polymerization. A study by Drakos et al.
330 (2021) on the characterization of wheat flour enhanced with inulin discovered that adding
331 inulin reduced the water absorption of the dough. Lower hygroscopicity could improve
332 the stability of these microcapsules during storage, particularly in humid conditions,
333 making them suitable for applications where moisture sensitivity is a concern. While
334 PPIGG (181.98 ± 1.82 g/100 g) microcapsules exhibited hygroscopicity values slightly
335 higher and potato protein isolate-soluble fiber (PPISF) (177.14 ± 1.78 g/100 g)
336 microcapsules were lower than SBGA and PPIGA. The high molecular weight and water-
337 binding solid capacity of guar gum, along with similar properties of soluble fiber, may
338 account for the increased hygroscopicity observed in these systems [31].

339 3.5. **Particle size dispersion**

340 The Span index, which measures the width of the particle size distribution, indicated that
341 PPIGA had the lowest Span index (1.66 ± 0.02), suggesting the most uniform particle size
342 distribution among the samples (Table 1). The stabilizing effect of guar gum and gum
343 Arabic likely contributes to the formation of coacervates with a more regulated size
344 distribution [34]. On the other hand, the higher Span index of PPII microcapsules ($2.61 \pm$
345 0.15) reflects less homogeneity and a broader particle size dispersion. The diameter of
346 microcapsules varied significantly from $78.89 \mu\text{m}$ to $403.30 \mu\text{m}$. The PPII microcapsules
347 exhibited the largest mean diameter ($403.30 \pm 11.09 \mu\text{m}$), whereas the PPIGG
348 microcapsules had the most minor mean diameter ($78.89 \pm 4.04 \mu\text{m}$). A broader particle
349 size distribution may result from the interaction between inulin and potato protein isolate,
350 leading to the formation of larger aggregates. This more excellent dispersion can impact
351 the release kinetics and stability of encapsulated anthocyanins, thereby making these
352 microcapsules appropriate for uses requiring a delayed release [35].

353 3.6. Microcapsule solubility

354 The PPIP microcapsules exhibited the highest solubility at $88.86 \pm 0.75\%$, closely
355 followed by SBGA at $88.49 \pm 1.56\%$. In contrast, the PPIGA and PPISF microcapsules
356 showed similar solubility values at $86.54 \pm 0.60\%$ and $87.37 \pm 1.51\%$, respectively,
357 indicating no significant differences in solubility between these samples. The PPIGG
358 microcapsules showed the lowest solubility, $23.49 \pm 0.51\%$. This suggests that the type of
359 polysaccharide in combination with potato protein isolate can affect solubility
360 significantly, but in the cases of PPIP, SBGA, PPIGA, and PPISF, no significant
361 differences were observed.

362 The solubility results show substantial differences across the formulations, which
363 indicates how the polysaccharide type affects the microcapsules' solubility. The
364 microcapsules composed with PPIP exhibited the maximum solubility of $88.86 \pm 0.75\%$,
365 indicating that pectin, due to its well-established solubility and gelation characteristics,
366 produces an encapsulating matrix that is more soluble. Pectin is a polysaccharide that
367 forms soluble gels when exposed to water, allowing the microcapsules to dissolve more
368 easily. Because of its ability to dissolve and release the materials it encapsulates, pectin's
369 encapsulating matrix makes it an ideal choice for applications requiring high solubility
370 [36].

371 The solubility of the SBGA microcapsules was found to be high ($88.49 \pm 1.56\%$), which
372 aligns with gum Arabic's established characteristics as a strong stabilizer and emulsifier
373 that creates highly soluble complexes [12]. SBGA's high solubility is comparable to that

374 of PPIP, PPIGA, and PPISF, can be used in various food systems requiring rapid
375 dissolving.

376 The PPIGA ($86.54 \pm 0.60\%$) and PPISF ($87.37 \pm 1.51\%$) microcapsules also demonstrated
377 high solubility, showing the potential of potato protein isolate combined with various
378 polysaccharides to form soluble microcapsules. The PPII formulation ($82.01 \pm 0.99\%$)
379 showed slightly lower solubility, which can be attributed to the inherent properties of
380 inulin. Inulin is a dietary fiber that can form viscous gels when hydrated, which may have
381 impeded the dissolution of the microcapsules to some extent [37]. The PPIGG
382 microcapsules displayed a much-reduced solubility ($23.49 \pm 0.51\%$). The low solubility
383 may be related to the properties of guar gum, which, when hydrated, generates a very
384 viscous gel that may impede the microcapsules' ability to dissolve. Guar gum's strong
385 gelling qualities and sizeable molecular weight probably contribute to its decreased
386 solubility in this environment [38].

387 3.7. Antioxidant activity evaluation

388 The DPPH• radical scavenging technique evaluated the antioxidant activities of
389 microcapsules. The results showed significant differences across the various formulations,
390 with the antioxidant activity represented in $\mu\text{mol trolox/g}$ (Table 1). The PPISF
391 microcapsules exhibited the highest level of antioxidant activity ($12.10 \pm 1.63 \mu\text{mol}$
392 trolox/g), while the SBGA microcapsules had the lowest level of activity (1.15 ± 0.41
393 $\mu\text{mol trolox/g}$).

394 The increased activity indicates that the antioxidant characteristics of black
395 carrot anthocyanins are proficiently maintained when potato protein isolate and soluble
396 fiber are integrated. Soluble fiber may improve the durability and efficacy of
397 encapsulation to preserve the bioactivity of anthocyanins. High antioxidant activities were
398 also shown by the PPIGA ($8.64 \pm 2.85 \mu\text{mol trolox/g}$) and PPIP ($8.36 \pm 0.81 \mu\text{mol}$
399 trolox/g) microcapsules. The stabilizing qualities of gum Arabic and pectin are well-
400 known, and they probably contribute to effectively protecting and sustaining the
401 antioxidant attributes of black carrot anthocyanins [39]. The potent antioxidant activity of
402 these formulations suggests that they might be used in nutraceuticals and functional foods,
403 which prioritize antioxidant qualities. The antioxidant activity levels of the PPIGG and
404 PPII microcapsules were similarly moderate, at $5.91 \mu\text{mol trolox/g}$. Compared to gum
405 Arabic and pectin, guar gum and inulin may offer less protection, resulting in a modest
406 preservation of antioxidant activity. Despite this, these formulations provide enough
407 antioxidant protection for various applications [35,40].

408 **3.8.** In contrast, SBGA microcapsules demonstrated the lowest antioxidant activity (1.15 ± 0.41
409 $\mu\text{mol trolox/g}$). The reduced activity may be attributed to the lower effectiveness of soybean
410 protein compared to potato protein-based systems in encapsulating and stabilizing
411 anthocyanins [41]. The significantly reduced antioxidant activity is an unexpected finding,
412 considering the position of soy protein as an effective emulsifier. Teng et al. [42] found that
413 the capacity of the protein molecules to adsorb at the interface diminished when the
414 concentration of soy protein isolate was over a certain point, which led to a decrease in
415 stability. Structural changes in soy proteins during emulsification may impair their ability to
416 encapsulate and protect anthocyanins, leading to the lower antioxidant activity observed in
417 SBGA microcapsules. **Stability of anthocyanin**

418 The DI of anthocyanins during a 420-minute period at three distinct pH levels (pH 1, pH
419 4, and pH 7) is displayed in Figure 1A. The findings unequivocally show that pH has a
420 major impact on the stability of anthocyanins. The anthocyanins showed the most stability
421 at pH 1, with the DI staying low at 0.3 for the whole 420 minutes. This finding suggests
422 that anthocyanins are highly stable in environments with high acidity. A considerable
423 degree of deterioration was seen at pH 4, where the DI progressively dropped during 420
424 minutes, from about 0.8 to around 0.6. This implies that anthocyanins are not as stable at
425 pH 1 but are still quite stable at this Ph [43].

426 On the other hand, the DI at pH 7 showed the highest reduction, starting at about 1.2 and
427 falling to 0.8 by 420 minutes. This significant reduction underscores the instability of
428 anthocyanins in neutral conditions, leading to rapid loss of color and structural integrity,
429 as noted in the literature. The consensus among researchers indicates that anthocyanins
430 are more stable in acidic environments and easily degraded in neutral and alkaline pH
431 ranges [42,43].

432 The DI of anthocyanins at two different temperatures (25°C and 90°C) during 180 minutes
433 is shown in Figure 2B. The findings show that temperature has an apparent impact on the
434 stability of anthocyanins. The greater slope of the DI curve at 90°C illustrates that the
435 deterioration occurred more quickly than it did at 25°C . After 180 minutes, the DI values
436 for 90°C dropped from around 0.4 to about 0.3, suggesting a loss of stability at higher
437 temperatures [46]. On the other hand, anthocyanin degradation was more slow at 25°C ,
438 as DI dropped from around 0.7 to 0.6 in the same time frame. This demonstrates that
439 anthocyanins degrade faster at higher temperatures, resulting in a greater DI, whereas they
440 are more stable at lower temperatures. The findings align with established research
441 indicating that anthocyanins are particularly susceptible to heat degradation, where

442 increased thermal energy catalyzes their breakdown, leading to diminished color intensity
 443 and structural integrity [47].
 444 Overall, the data show that pH and temperature have a significant impact on anthocyanin
 445 stability. More acidic and lower temperatures preserve anthocyanin structure better, which
 446 is important for preserving the color and bioactive qualities of anthocyanins in food and
 447 nutraceutical applications.

448 **Fig.1.** Effect of A) pH and B) temperature on the degradation index (DI) of BC
 449 anthocyanins as a function of time.
 450
 451

452 3.9. Encapsulation efficiency evaluation

453 The MEE results for the different microcapsule formulations are presented in Table 1. The
 454 MEE values ranged from 64.00% to 81.20%. The highest MEE was observed in the
 455 PPIGA microcapsules as $81.20 \pm 8.39\%$. This enhanced performance can be explained by
 456 gum Arabic's distinct film-forming and emulsifying qualities that function in combination
 457 with potato protein isolate to build a strong encapsulation matrix [48]. In the study,
 458 because of the strong electrostatic interactions and hydrogen bonds between the
 459 components, the PPIGA system may be highly effective in entrapping and stabilizing
 460 anthocyanins, as indicated by the high encapsulation efficiency.

461 Pectin is another polysaccharide that creates an effective encapsulation matrix when
 462 mixed with potato protein isolate. This is demonstrated by the high MEE ($80.86 \pm 2.73\%$)
 463 of the PPIP system. Due to pectin's capacity to form gels and its interactions with proteins,
 464 anthocyanin encapsulation and stability may be improved, leading to high MEE values.
 465 According to the study of Pan et al. [49], employing a combination of soy protein isolates
 466 and high methyl pectin significantly increased the encapsulation efficiency (EE) of
 467 blueberry anthocyanins by around 93.5%. This was higher than employing SPI or whey
 468 protein isolates alone, which achieved 80.2% and 75.1% encapsulation efficiencies,

469 respectively. In addition to improving encapsulation effectiveness, the combined wall
470 materials also improved other physicochemical characteristics, such as decreased particle
471 size and hygroscopicity, which suggest improved storage stability and reduced moisture
472 content.

473 The encapsulation efficiencies of the PPISF, PPIGG, and PPII microcapsules were
474 similarly comparatively high, indicating the adaptability of potato protein isolate in
475 creating efficient encapsulation systems with different polysaccharides. It has been
476 reported that guar gum's high viscosity and gel-forming capacity can improve the
477 microcapsules' mechanical strength and stability. This characteristic contributes to
478 increased encapsulation efficiency by preserving the integrity of the encapsulated
479 substance during processing and storage. Van der Waals forces and hydrophobic
480 interactions are two examples of non-covalent interactions that guar gum can use to
481 interact with potato protein isolate despite being a non-ionic polysaccharide [50–52]. A
482 stable encapsulation matrix may be formed as a result of these interactions.

483 The SBGA microcapsules, on the other hand, had the lowest MEE with $64.00 \pm 4.97\%$. The
484 relatively low encapsulation efficiency might be attributed to the intrinsic differences between
485 isolates of potato and soybean proteins as well as the unique interactions between gum Arabic
486 and soybean protein, which could not be as effective in generating a robust encapsulation matrix
487 as the systems based on potato proteins. The chemical structure of anthocyanins, which includes
488 a flavylium cation core and different sugar and acyl moieties, makes them susceptible to
489 hydrolysis, oxidation, and other degrading mechanisms [46]. Anthocyanins may preferentially
490 remain in the continuous aqueous phase rather than being fully integrated into the oil droplets,
491 making the partitioning between the aqueous and oil phases difficult [53,54].

Table 1: Characterization of Microcapsules Encapsulating Black Carrot Anthocyanins

Samples	Moisture content (%)	Hygroscopicity (g/100 g)	Span	CE Diameter (4,3) (μm)	Microcapsule Solubility (MS) (%)	DPPH(μmol trolox/g)	MEE (%)
SB:GA	1.14±0.30 ^{ab}	179.29±3.00 ^{abc}	2.12±0.02 ^b	104.98±15.80 ^{ab}	88.49±1.56 ^a	1.15±0.41 ^b	64.00±4.97 ^a
PPI:GA	1.72±0.63 ^b	179.22±3.09 ^{abc}	1.66±0.02 ^a	114.90±14.96 ^{ab}	86.54±0.60 ^a	8.64±2.85 ^a	81.20±8.39 ^b
PPI:GG	0.04±0.02 ^a	181.98±1.82 ^{bc}	2.11±0.03 ^{ab}	78.89±4.04 ^a	23.49±0.51 ^b	5.91±1.43 ^{ab}	79.00±6.96 ^{ab}
PPI:I	0.95±0.03 ^{ab}	170.48±2.58 ^a	2.61±0.15 ^{ab}	403.30±11.09 ⁱ	82.01±0.99 ^c	5.91±1.05 ^{ab}	67.28±3.72 ^{ab}
PPI:P	0.64±0.15 ^{ab}	188.15±3.36 ^c	1.93±0.07 ^a	88.35±3.16 ^{ab}	88.86±0.75 ^a	8.36±0.81 ^a	80.86±2.73 ^{ab}
PPI:SF	0.50±0.14 ^a	177.14±1.78 ^{ab}	2.60±0.01 ^a	247.00±7.11 ^c	87.37±1.51 ^a	12.10±1.63 ^a	79.03±8.37 ^{ab}

Values are means ± standard deviations. Different superscript letters in the column indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

1 3.10. Thermal properties

2 The thermal properties of the microcapsules were characterized using DSC. Table 2 provides the
3 enthalpy change (ΔH), onset temperature (T_{on}), peak temperature (T_{max}), and end temperature
4 (T_{end}) for the different microcapsule formulations. The DSC study offers critical information on
5 the temperature stability and phase transitions of the microcapsules. The onset, peak, and end
6 temperatures, along with the enthalpy changes, reflect the interactions between the encapsulated
7 anthocyanins and the protein-polysaccharide matrices.

8 The amount of energy absorbed or released during the thermal process is measured by the
9 enthalpy change (ΔH). Endothermic processes are indicated by positive ΔH values, whereas
10 exothermic activities are indicated by negative values. While PPIGA, PPIGG, and PPIP had
11 negative ΔH values, indicating exothermic transitions, SBGA, PPII, and PPISF formulations
12 showed positive ΔH values, indicating endothermic transitions.

13 Higher onset temperatures imply greater thermal stability. The onset temperature (T_{on}) marks the
14 start of thermal processes like melting or degradation. PPIGA was the sample with the highest
15 onset temperature, suggesting that it was more thermally stable than the other formulations. . This
16 high thermal stability is attributed to the robust encapsulation matrix formed by the strong
17 interactions between gum Arabic and potato protein isolate [55]. The nature and concentration of
18 the wall materials, as well as the encapsulation techniques employed, play a crucial role in
19 determining the thermal stability of the final product. In the study of Deng et al. [56], the thermal
20 and storage stability of purple corn anthocyanins was also improved by protecting in a matrix of
21 gum Arabic, maltodextrin, and whey protein isolate.

22 The temperature at which the thermal event happens at its highest rate is known as the peak
23 temperature (T_{max}). PPIGG, with the highest T_{max} , indicates that the formulation's encapsulated
24 anthocyanins undergo phase transitions at higher temperatures, making them suitable for
25 applications requiring high-temperature stability. When comparing the formulations, SBGA
26 demonstrated significant thermal stability, with an onset temperature of 141.32°C and a peak
27 temperature of 170.04°C. The positive enthalpy shift indicates an endothermic transition, which
28 might be attributed to the melting of the encapsulating matrix. The high thermal stability of this
29 formulation indicates that the encapsulation matrix formed by the soy bean-gum arabic
30 combination is effective in protecting the encapsulated components from thermal degradation
31 [57].

32 With a peak temperature of 173.16°C and the maximum onset temperature of 168.79°C, PPIGA
 33 showed excellent thermal stability. Exothermic transitions, which might be connected to the
 34 encapsulation matrix's degradation, are shown by the negative enthalpy change [58,59]. The
 35 temperature of PPIGG was moderate at 166.10°C and high at 192.39°C at its peak. The negative
 36 enthalpy change indicates exothermic activities, which might be the result of structural
 37 rearrangements inside the matrix. PPII was characterized by a high peak temperature and a lower
 38 start temperature, suggesting a substantial thermal event at a higher temperature. The positive
 39 enthalpy change indicates an endothermic transition. The formulation with PPIP had the greatest
 40 onset temperature compared to rest of the samples, suggesting strong thermal stability.
 41 Exothermic transitions, perhaps brought on by matrix degradation, are shown by the negative
 42 enthalpy change. Finally, PPISF showed high thermal stability, reaching a peak temperature of
 43 182.35°C and an onset temperature of 151.93°C.

44 The DSC results highlight the importance of selecting appropriate polysaccharides to enhance
 45 the thermal stability and performance of microcapsules. The high onset and peak temperatures of
 46 PPIGA and PPIP formulations suggest that gum Arabic and pectin are effective in providing
 47 thermal stability to the encapsulated anthocyanins. Understanding these thermal properties is
 48 crucial for developing microcapsules that can withstand processing and storage conditions,
 49 ensuring the stability and bioavailability of the encapsulated bioactive compounds.

50 **Table 2.** DSC analysis results for obtained samples.

Samples	Enthalpy ($\Delta H - J \cdot g^{-1}$)	T_{on} [°C]	T_{max} [°C]	T_{end} [°C]
SB:GA	3.73 x 10 ⁻⁵	141.32	170.04	251.54
PPI:GA	-324.6	168.79	173.16	251.32
PPI:GG	-228.1	166.10	192.39	251.79
PPI:I	2.21 x 10 ⁻⁵	140.53	193.33	200.30
PPI:P	-210.4	171.10	177.79	244.73
PPI:SF	26.33 x 10 ⁻⁵	151.93	182.35	257.47

51

Fig. 2. Entire infrared spectra pattern (A) and second derivate of spectra of coacervates from 800 to 1800 cm⁻¹

1 3.11. Chemical Interaction and Structural Analysis Using FT-IR

2
3 The FT-IR spectra of the coacervates were analyzed to identify functional groups
4 and chemical interactions between the potato protein isolate and various polysaccharides.
5 The infrared spectra pattern (Fig. 2, A) and second derivative (Fig. 2, B) of coacervates
6 from 800 to 1800 cm^{-1} give a complete insight into the molecular interactions within the
7 coacervate system. The presence and interaction of proteins and polysaccharides in the
8 microcapsules are highlighted by the distinctive peaks in the spectra that correspond to
9 different functional groups (Fig. 2, A). The prominent absorption peak at 3300 cm^{-1}
10 appears in all samples and indicates O-H stretching vibrations [60]. Because of hydrogen
11 bonding, this area is usually broad and represents the amount of hydroxyl groups found
12 in polysaccharides. The interaction of wall materials can be increased by forming
13 hydrogen bonds, which may increase the ability to retain microcapsules' structural
14 integrity and stability [61]. The Amide I band, which comprises distinct peaks close to
15 1650 cm^{-1} , is the C=O stretching vibration of the amide groups in proteins [62]. The
16 Amide I band's existence and strength demonstrate how effectively the coacervate system
17 incorporates protein isolates, which is necessary to create a durable coacervate matrix.
18 Furthermore, the Amide II band, or N-H bending and C-N stretching vibrations of the
19 amide groups, are represented by peaks at around 1550 cm^{-1} [63]. This is similar to the
20 results from Han, Li, et al. (2024), which emphasize the significance of interactions
21 between proteins and polysaccharides in creating stable encapsulation systems.

22 Around 1000 cm^{-1} , prominent peaks show the characteristic C-O and C-C
23 stretching vibrations in carbohydrate structures. This observation is supported by the
24 study of Todorović et al. [64], which highlighted the importance of carbohydrates in the
25 encapsulation and stability of diverse bioactive chemicals. The carbohydrate content is
26 essential in encapsulation because it produces a dense matrix capable of trapping and
27 stabilizing anthocyanins.

28 The second derivative FT-IR spectra (Fig. 2, B) improved the resolution of
29 overlapping bands, particularly in the 800-1800 cm^{-1} range. The second derivative spectra
30 showed clear peaks in the Amide I and II areas. The peaks in the Amide I and Amide II
31 areas were more prominent, indicating differences in protein secondary structures across
32 samples. These peaks show differences in the interactions between the different
33 polysaccharides in each formulation and the protein isolates. For example, a sample with
34 stronger protein-polysaccharide connections and a more persistent coacervate matrix may

35 have greater intensity in the Amide I area [65,66]. The second derivative spectrum also
36 revealed minor differences in the region containing carbohydrates (around 1000 cm⁻¹).
37 These variations can give information on the specific types of polysaccharides present
38 and how they interact inside the coacervate system.

39 The FT-IR spectra in the 960-1180 cm⁻¹ region primarily show absorptions due to
40 C-O and C-C stretching vibrations, which indicate carbohydrate content [67]. The peak
41 area for this region varied significantly among samples (Table 2). SBGA had the most
42 prominent peak area, indicating a high carbohydrate content. This suggests that the soy
43 protein-gum Arabic combination contains many carbohydrates. Gum Arabic, a complex
44 polymer composed of arabinose, galactose, rhamnose, and glucuronic acid, has a naturally
45 high carbohydrate content, likely explaining the higher carbohydrate content in the SBGA
46 coacervates [68]. PPII had the lowest peak area, indicative of a reduced carbohydrate
47 content. The differences in this peak area reflect the effectiveness of various
48 polysaccharides in maintaining carbohydrate structures within coacervates [69].

49 In the Amide I region, which is related to the C=O stretching vibration of proteins,
50 PPIP exhibited the highest peak area, indicating a high concentration of protein
51 components. This suggests that pectin enhances the protein network in the coacervates by
52 efficiently interacting with potato protein isolate [70,71]. On the other hand, PPISF
53 showed the smallest peak area, showing limited protein interaction in this formulation.
54 These findings demonstrate the range of protein-polysaccharide interactions and the
55 influence of different polysaccharides on the structural integrity of coacervates.

56 The carbonyl region had the highest peak area in PPIGA, showing that potato
57 protein isolate and gum Arabic interacted strongly. It is essential to consider this
58 interaction to create stable coacervates with high encapsulation efficiency [72]. With the
59 lowest carbonyl peak area, PPISF may have lessened the interactions between soluble
60 fiber and potato protein isolate, which might impact the microcapsule's durability. With
61 the lowest carbonyl peak area, PPISF may have less effect on the stability of the
62 microcapsule by indicating a reduced connection between potato protein isolate and
63 soluble fiber.

64 The hydroxyl and amine stretching regions indicate the presence of O-H and N-H
65 bonds. The most prominent peak area of SBGA observed strong hydrogen bonding and
66 a high hydroxyl group concentration. The soy protein-gum Arabic combination
67 may create a highly hydrated network that protects hydrophilic anthocyanins [65]. PPISF
68 exhibited the smallest peak area and may show fewer hydrogen bonds and probably less

69 water content in this coacervate system. The variations observed in the hydroxyl/amine
 70 stretching area indicate a considerable influence of the polysaccharide type on the stability
 71 and hydration of coacervates [73].

72 Overall, potato protein-polysaccharide coacervate systems, particularly those
 73 including gum Arabic and pectin, show promise for improving the stability and
 74 bioavailability of anthocyanin. The FT-IR analysis provides extensive information on
 75 coacervates' molecular interactions and structural integrity.

77 **Table 3.** Spectral band areas for coacervates in various FT-IR regions.

Samples	Spectral band range, cm ⁻¹			
	Carbohydrates Peak Area (960-1180 cm ⁻¹)	Amide I Peak Area (1570-1700 cm ⁻¹)	Amide I / Carbonyl Peak Area (1718-1762 cm ⁻¹)	Hydroxyl/Amine Stretching Peak Area (3050-3600 cm ⁻¹)
SB:GA	50.09±0.18 ^b	1.86±0.03 ^c	0.81±0.01 ^{ab}	34.45±0.28 ^d
PPI:GA	45.44±0.25 ^{ab}	0.73±0.02 ^b	1.23±0.02 ^e	27.74±0.46 ^a
PPI:GG	45.97±0.10 ^{ab}	0.81±0.01 ^b	1.01±0.03 ^{cd}	28.44±0.41 ^a
PPI:I	37.54±0.34 ^c	0.23±0.01 ^a	0.92±0.03 ^{bc}	15.30±0.56 ^b
PPI:P	44.13±5.52 ^{ab}	2.15±0.15 ^d	1.04±0.09 ^d	28.36±2.39 ^a
PPI:SF	42.89±0.19 ^{ac}	0.09±0.00 ^a	0.74±0.02 ^a	21.85±0.44 ^c

78 The table presents various samples' peak areas corresponding to different spectral regions (Carbohydrates, Amide I,
 79 Carbonyl, and Hydroxyl/Amine). The values are given as mean ± standard deviation. Different superscripts within
 80 the same column indicate statistically significant differences (p < 0.05) among the samples.

81

82 3.12. Surface morphology analysis

83

Fig. 3. Scanning electron micrographs of microcapsules. Magnification of 2500x

84
 85
 86
 87 Fig. 3 presents the SEM images for the different microcapsule formulations. The SEM analysis
 88 reveals significant differences in the surface morphology and structural characteristics of the
 89 microcapsules based on the type of polysaccharide used for encapsulation.
 90 The SEM picture of SBGA reveals microcapsules with a rough surface and uneven forms, which
 91 indicates that the encapsulation matrix is less consistent due to the combination of gum Arabic
 92 and soybean protein. This may affect the stability of anthocyanins and release characteristics
 93 when encapsulated, which might result in less successful encapsulation when compared to other
 94 formulations [56]. The study of Ribeiro et al. [32] noted that particles exhibited a range of
 95 morphologies from spherical to irregular shapes, with significant levels of aggregation and rough
 96 surfaces, particularly when gum Arabic and maltodextrin were used as encapsulating agents.
 97 Compared to SBGA, the PPIGA microcapsules have a more homogeneous and compact structure
 98 and a comparatively smooth surface. The surface of the PPIGA microcapsules is more consistent,
 99 suggesting that gum Arabic when mixed with potato protein isolate, helps generate regular
 100 microcapsules. This consistency can improve the durability of microcapsules and consistency in
 101 food applications, giving the encapsulated anthocyanins better protection.
 102 The granular and clustered appearance of PPIGG microcapsules is indicative of the dense and
 103 compact microcapsules formed by guar gum. By decreasing the exposed surface area, this shape
 104 may enhance the stability of the encapsulated anthocyanins. However, it may also affect the
 105 release kinetics, making these microcapsules appropriate for applications requiring controlled
 106 release [74]. The surface of PPII microcapsules is sandy, with big, irregular particles. The PPII
 107 microcapsules have uneven surfaces, possibly due to the less efficient interaction of potato protein
 108 isolate with inulin. Larger aggregates and a fractured structure are the outcomes that may have
 109 an impact on the stability of anthocyanins and encapsulation effectiveness. In the case of PPIP,
 110 the microcapsules have a rough surface and uneven forms, yet they appear to be more densely

111 packed than SBGA. Pectin can potentially enhance the encapsulation matrix's stability and
112 improve the regulated release and preservation of anthocyanins [8].

113 The PPISF microcapsules exhibit a highly aggregated, granular surface, which may suggest that
114 soluble fiber encourages the development of tightly packed microcapsules. Because of their tight
115 packing, these microcapsules are appropriate for applications requiring high stability, which can
116 improve the stability and protection of the encapsulated anthocyanins.

117 Our SEM analysis of the microcapsules showed morphological features that align with the results
118 published by Machado et al. [75], who investigated spray drying to microencapsulate
119 anthocyanin-rich extract from red cabbage. Their SEM micrographs revealed spherical
120 microparticles with smooth surfaces, some of which had wrinkled walls and concave
121 collapses, similar to our observations. These surface irregularities, which resembled the granular
122 and clustered appearance observed in PPIGG microcapsules, were explained as the result of
123 shrinking during the drying procedures.

124 3.13. Color parameters

138 **Fig. 4** Images of microcapsules encapsulating black carrot anthocyanins

139
140 The color characteristics (L^* , a^* , and b^*) of anthocyanin-loaded coacervates produced by various
141 protein-polysaccharide combinations were examined to determine their effect on the appearance
142 of the encapsulated anthocyanins. The findings in Table 4 and Figure 4 show notable differences
143 in color characteristics between the various formulations.

144 The samples differed considerably in the L^* value, which represents lightness. The SBGA
145 microcapsules exhibited the highest L^* value, representing their lightest color, whereas the PPISF
146 microcapsules had the lowest L^* value, signifying their darker hue. Significant variations across
147 the samples were also observed in the red-green spectrum represented by the a^* value. The PPISF
148 microcapsules had the highest recorded a^* value, suggesting a more intense red color, whereas
149 the PPIP microcapsules had the lowest a^* value, suggesting a less intense red color. The PPISF
150 microcapsules demonstrated a positive b^* value, suggesting a shift towards yellow, whereas the
151 other samples showed negative b^* values, indicating a shift towards blue. The b^* value measures
152 the yellow-blue spectrum. The PPIP microcapsules had the lowest b^* value, indicating a more
153 prominent blue color.

154 The inherent properties of the polysaccharides and their interaction with anthocyanins might
155 be responsible for the variance in brightness. While the darker appearance of PPI variations
156 shows that soluble fiber generates a less transparent matrix, possibly due to its interaction with
157 anthocyanins, SBGA's higher lightness is likely due to gum Arabic's ability to build a more
158 transparent matrix surrounding the anthocyanins [12]. Significant variation was seen in the a^*
159 values, with the PPISF microcapsules displaying the essential value. This suggests a deeper red
160 hue, which may result from interactions between the soluble fiber and potato protein isolate that
161 improve the anthocyanins' stability and encapsulation efficiency [74,76]. In contrast, PPIP
162 microcapsules may have less successful stabilization or encapsulation, as seen by their lower a^*
163 values, which would result in a less vivid red color.

164 The b^* values further confirmed significant differences between the samples. The shift towards
165 yellow, shown by the positive b^* value in PPISF microcapsules, might perhaps be attributed to
166 the combined influence of soluble fiber and potato protein isolate on the anthocyanin
167 encapsulation process. However, the samples with negative b^* values have a blue hue,
168 most prominently in PPIP microcapsules. The overall color of the encapsulated anthocyanins may
169 be affected by the unique way that potato protein interacts with polysaccharides such as guar
170 gum, inulin, and other polysaccharides.

171
172 The color analysis shows that the type of polysaccharide and protein utilized in the coacervate
173 method significantly influences the encapsulated anthocyanins' color characteristics. These
174 results imply that anthocyanin-containing microcapsules can have their visual characteristics
175 customized by carefully choosing protein-polysaccharide combinations, which may increase their
176 attractiveness and use in food items.

177

178 **Table 4.** Color Parameters (L^* , a^* , and b^*) of Anthocyanin-Loaded Coacervates Formed by
 179 Different Protein-Polysaccharide Combinations

	L^*	a^*	b^*
SB:GA	66.53±0.09 ^e	28.40±0.04 ^c	-2.74±0.07 ^b
PPI:GA	62.57±0.25 ^a	35.58±0.02 ^e	-0.52±0.04 ^e
PPI:GG	61.26±0.24 ^c	31.11±0.02 ^d	-1.27±0.01 ^d
PPI:I	62.80±0.16 ^a	28.19±0.02 ^b	-2.24±0.02 ^c
PPI:P	65.13±0.15 ^d	25.85±0.05 ^a	-4.32±0.02 ^a
PPI:SF	55.11±0.15 ^b	36.68±0.09 ^f	0.65±0.01 ^f

180 Values are means ± standard deviations (n=3). Different superscript letters within each column indicate significant
 181 differences ($p < 0.05$).

182 14. HPLC

183 The retention capabilities of individual anthocyanins, including: Cyanidin-3-(6"-
 184 malonylglucoside)-5-(6"-succinylglucoside) (Cy-3-XGG), Cyanidin-3-xylosylglucoside (Cy-3-
 185 XG), Sinapic Acid Acylated Cyanidin-3-xylosylglucoside (SA-Cy-3-XGG), Ferulic Acid
 186 Acylated Cyanidin-3-xylosylglucoside (FA-Cy-3-XGG), and Caffeic Acid Acylated Cyanidin-3-
 187 xylosylglucoside (CA-Cy-3-XGG), were evaluated using High-Performance Liquid
 188 Chromatography-Ultraviolet Detection (HPLC-UV) and HPLC-tandem Mass Spectrometry
 189 (HPLC-MS/MS). The results are summarized in Table 5.

190 The retention capabilities of individual anthocyanins in various formulations reveal significant
 191 differences in the efficiency of the encapsulation matrices. These differences can be attributed to
 192 the molecular interactions between the anthocyanins and the protein-polysaccharide matrices, as
 193 well as the structural properties of the polysaccharides used.

194 All anthocyanins showed comparably high retention rates for SBGA, with Cy-3-XGG and Cy-3-
 195 XG showing the highest retention rates. Gum Arabic is well-known for its superior film-forming
 196 and emulsifying abilities, which work to stabilize anthocyanins by encapsulating them in a barrier
 197 of protection [12]. While the matrix is generally efficient, particular interactions with some
 198 anthocyanins may be less strong, as indicated by the modest preservation of other anthocyanins.

199 Lower retention capacity was demonstrated by PPIGA, particularly for SA-Cy-3-XGG and FA-
 200 Cy-3-XGG. This suggests that the potato protein isolate-gum Arabic combination stabilizes the

201 mixture less effectively, with weakened connections or an insufficient matrix structure for these
202 particular anthocyanins. While potato protein forms a generally more stable encapsulation matrix
203 with gum Arabic, specific anthocyanin molecules may preferentially interact with soy proteins,
204 leading to higher retention capabilities for anthocyanins in the soy protein-based system. This
205 variation is influenced by the chemical nature of the anthocyanins, which may favor different
206 protein matrices depending on the molecular structure of the polysaccharides and the proteins
207 involved[77–79].

208 PPIGG exhibited remarkable retention capacity for both SA-Cy-3-XGG and FA-Cy-3-XGG,
209 demonstrating a possible matrix effect in which the combination of potato protein isolate and
210 guar gum not only stabilizes but also potentially improves the retention of these anthocyanins. In
211 a study by Rosales-Murillo et al. [80], the combination of potato starch, turnip peel anthocyanins,
212 and guar gum-cinnamaldehyde was found to enhance the stability and antimicrobial properties of
213 anthocyanins, demonstrating the potential for similar stabilization mechanisms in our
214 encapsulation systems using potato protein isolate and guar gum. Guar gum can provide a more
215 cohesive and protective matrix because of its high viscosity and ability to bind water. The poor
216 retention for Cy-3-XG, on the other hand, indicates a possible interaction difficulty with this
217 anthocyanin, either because of hydrophilicity differences or steric hindrance. The hydrophilicity
218 properties of the Cy-3-XG anthocyanin may differ from those of the other anthocyanins
219 evaluated, which may have an impact on how effectively it is encapsulated and retained within
220 the PPIGG matrix. The encapsulation efficiency depends mostly on the interaction between the
221 hydrophilic/hydrophobic characteristics of the anthocyanin and the matrix components [81].

222 PPIP had the highest overall retention capacity among all anthocyanins, notably for Cy-3-XG and
223 Cy-3-XGG. The strong and stable matrix that pectin can build around the anthocyanins is a result
224 of its exceptional film-forming qualities and gel-forming capacity. The high retention rates show
225 that pectin combines with potato protein isolate to generate a strong encapsulation system that
226 offers the anthocyanins better stability and protection [82].

227 The maximum retention capacity for PPII was found in FA-Cy-3-XGG, with overall lower
228 retention capacities. As a fructan with prebiotic qualities, inulin may not be as effective in
229 encapsulating and stabilizing anthocyanins as other polysaccharides due to its reduced molecular
230 weight and less capacity to form films [83]. With the decreased retention, inulin may not offer
231 enough protection against stressful conditions.

232 PPISF had a high retention rate for Cy-3-XGG but less retention for other anthocyanins,
 233 particularly SA-Cy-3-XGG and FA-Cy-3-XGG. The characteristics of soluble fiber can differ
 234 based on the source, however in general, they might not create a matrix as strong as guar gum or
 235 pectin [84]. Because of variations in chemical interactions and matrix structure, it is possible that
 236 some anthocyanins are more effectively stabilized by the soluble fiber-formed matrix than by
 237 others.

238 **Table 5.** Retention capabilities individual anthocyanins

Samples	Cy-3-XGG (%)	Cy-3-XG (%)	SA-Cy-3-XGG (%)	FA-Cy-3-XGG (%)	CA-Cy-3-XGG (%)
SB:GA	85.60 ±4.71 ^{ab}	88.10 ±0.74 ^d	67.90 ±0.33 ^d	66.80 ±0.13 ^a	62.30±0.87 ^a
PPI:GA	73.90 ±7.28 ^d	63.30 ±0.47 ^a	26.50 ±0.12 ^a	20.50 ±0.04 ^b	23.20±0.29 ^b
PPI:GG	83.40 ±8.11 ^a	4.58 ±0.02 ^b	102.90 ±0.25 ^f	122.80 ±0.12 ^e	109.30 ±0.77 ^e
PPI:I	42.50 ±5.45 ^c	51.90 ±0.55 ^a	54.50 ±0.33 ^c	73.90 ±0.18 ^a	58.40 ±1.02 ^a
PPI:P	93.70 ±11.62 ^b	99.80 ±0.90 ^e	70.00 ±0.36 ^e	86.90 ±0.18 ^d	91.90 ±1.37 ^d
PPI:SF	85.30 ±3.23 ^a	79.50 ±0.64 ^c	33.30 ±0.16 ^b	35.00 ±0.07 ^c	37.90 ±0.51 ^c

239 Values are means ± standard deviations. Different superscript letters in the column indicate significant differences
 240 ($p < 0.05$). Different superscript letters indicate significant differences among the samples for each measured
 241 parameter.

242

2434. Conclusion

244 This study shows that various polysaccharides significantly affect the characteristics of
 245 microcapsules based on potato protein isolate that includes anthocyanins from black carrots. The
 246 study results showed that pH significantly impacts potato protein solubility, with the protein being
 247 most soluble at highly acidic (pH 2) and least soluble close to the isoelectric point (pH 4-6).
 248 Analysis of the hygroscopicity and moisture content of the formulations showed significant
 249 variations, with PPIGG exhibiting the lowest moisture content, suggesting better stability and
 250 potential for longer shelf life, and PPIGA displaying the highest moisture content given the
 251 hygroscopic nature of gum Arabic.

252 Effective integration of proteins and polysaccharides was demonstrated by FT-IR
 253 analysis, which validated the existence of critical functional groups and interactions within the
 254 coacervate systems. Morphological differences were shown by SEM imaging, showing that

255 PPIGA and PPISF microcapsules were more uniformly shaped and compact. The visual
256 properties of the encapsulated anthocyanins were significantly influenced by the kind of
257 polysaccharide, as revealed by colorimetric examination. Despite the promising results, this study
258 has some drawbacks. The effect of external factors, such as temperature and humidity, on the
259 stability and performance of coacervates was not investigated. Furthermore, the encapsulated
260 anthocyanins' long-term stability and release kinetics demand further research.

261 Despite the promising outcomes, there are limitations to this study. The effects of external
262 factors such as temperature and humidity on the stability and performance of the coacervates
263 were not assessed. Additionally, the long-term stability of the encapsulated anthocyanins, as well
264 as their release kinetics, requires further investigation. Addressing these factors is essential for
265 understanding the full potential of the coacervate system in real-world applications.

266 In conclusion, PPI-based coacervate systems, particularly those including gum Arabic and
267 pectin, have a high potential for improving anthocyanin stability and bioavailability. Coacervate
268 formulations' functional characteristics and interactions have improved these discoveries, which
269 may help develop efficient encapsulation techniques for bioactive substances. Further
270 advancements in using these coacervate systems in the food and nutraceutical sectors can be
271 achieved by overcoming the highlighted constraints and exploring future research paths.

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275

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